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EFFECT OF INHALATION COMPLEX THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

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Abstract

The dynamics of ventilation parameters, as well as exercise tolerance, were studied in 78 patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease during treatment with glycerosin inhalation. In the course of the studies, a positive dynamics of ventilation indicators was established, all the main indicators of the function of external respiration improved, and tolerance to physical activity increased. Comprehensive treatment of patients with COPD using glycerosine inhalation (IG) leads to a significant reduction in a number of major clinical manifestations of the disease already during the first 10 days of treatment and continues throughout the course of therapy.

Keywords: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, respiratory function, physical tolerability, inhalations of glicerozini

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the most common diseases of the internal organs, it occurs in 5–7% of patients over 40 years of age and is one of the common causes of death (4). “The diagnosis of COPD in clinical practice requires objective spirometric evidence of airway obstruction that does not return to normal after treatment” (6). The main functional syndromes in COPD are: a violation of bronchial patency, a change in the structure of static volumes, a violation of the elastic properties and diffusion capacity of the lungs, and a decrease in physical performance.

The diagnosis of COPD is largely a functional diagnosis and it is quite natural that the methods that make it possible to identify exactly the violations of bronchial patency, determine their severity and degree of reversibility seem to be the most important and play a primary role in making the final clinical diagnosis, and ultimately make it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the ongoing treatment.

Due to the widespread prevalence of COPD, direct medical and indirect costs associated with morbidity and premature mortality can represent a serious economic and social problem for society, population and health authorities (3). Experts of the European Respiratory Society believe that adequate treatment, which requires significant financial costs, can significantly improve the quality and life expectancy of patients suffering from this chronic progressive disease. Currently, one of the main directions in the treatment of COPD is long-term bronchodilatory therapy, which can reduce the duration of symptoms of the disease, reduce the frequency and severity of exacerbations, and improve exercise tolerance and quality of life in patients.

The flora of our republic is rich in medicinal plants; among them we can distinguish licorice. Licorice has been used for a long time for diseases of the respiratory tract in the practice of oriental medicine. Avicenna very often mentioned licorice in his "Canons"

as a means of "facilitating the work of the bronchi, removing all sorts of fluids and mucus." Because of licorice extract - glycyrrhizic acid, a number of bronchodilator drugs were created. However, due to the advent of powerful secretory drugs, its use has faded into the background. On the other hand, the presence of mineralocorticoid abilities in HA seriously limited its use: when administered in therapeutically significant doses (300 mg per day), sodium and water retention and an increase in blood pressure were noted. Studies conducted in our Center have shown that glycyrrhizic acid, without being destroyed, penetrates into the body during its inhalation, also during electrophoresis from the anode, in an amount of up to 30%, is well deposited in the subcutaneous fat layer and has a resorptive effect (5). For this reason, the purpose of our research was to find and implement alternative ways to use this unique natural remedy in the complex therapy of COPD.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

To study the dynamics of ventilation parameters and exercise tolerance during treatment with glycerosine inhalation in the complex therapy of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in 78 patients with COPD in the acute stage. The mean age of the patients was 56.1 ± 1.9 years. There were 50 men and 28 women. All patients complained of cough (100%) with scanty sputum (58%) and shortness of breath (100%). 32 patients with COPD of varying severity were examined once during the first days of their stay in the clinic, the remaining 46 patients with COPD were examined upon admission to the hospital, after 10 days of complex treatment with the inclusion of IG.

Inhalation of glycerosin was carried out using the apparatus "compressor inhaler LD-2100", while 3 ml-3% solution of glycerosin + 3 ml of saline. solutions were included in the capacity of the inhaler for drugs

and the procedure through the mouthpiece continued for 10 minutes.

The selection of patients was carried out on the basis of a comprehensive examination, which included clinical, biochemical, immunological, instrumental research methods.

The state of the function of external respiration (RF) was studied according to pneumotachometry data. In the first days of hospital stay, after 10 days 2 times / day and after 1 month of inhalation of glycerosin 1 time / day. As functional indicators, we used vital capacity (VC), forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1), the ratio of forced expiratory volume in 1 second to vital capacity (FEV1/VC,%), peak expiratory flow (PEF), maximum forced expiratory rate at the level of 25%, 50%, 75% FVC (MOC25, MOC50, MOC75), total lung capacity (TLC), residual lung volume (ROL), ratio of residual volume to total lung capacity (ROL / TLC). To determine the degree of ventilation insufficiency

and exercise tolerance, a 6-minute walking test was performed, at the end of which the distance traveled in meters was estimated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the FVD, there was a decrease in the ventilation-perfusion state of the bronchopulmonary system in all patients with PH. Thus, the FEV1 index was $38.2 \pm 0.5\%$ in the 1st group, in the 2nd group. - $46.1 \pm 1.6\%$, ($p < 0.005$), SaO₂, respectively, in 1 - $85.1 \pm 5\%$ and in 2 $89.6 \pm 1.4\%$ ($p < 0.05$), which is typical for increase in bronchial obstruction.

The analysis of ventilation parameters in the group of patients who received IG showed its good efficiency, which was manifested by an increase in the studied main indicators of the function of external respiration. So, after 10 days of therapy with the inclusion of inhalation of glycerosin, an increase in volumetric indicators was noted.

Data from the 6-minute step test also showed a 12% increase in test performance after 10 days of drug use (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of ventilation parameters and exercise tolerance in patients with COPD on the background of complex treatment with IG

Indicators	Growth of the indicator, %	
	During treatment with IG	Control group
	After 10 days	After 10 days
VC	+15,8	-3,4
OФВ ₁	+25,4	+3,0
ПСВ	+22,7	-17
MOC ₂₅	+34	+1
MOC ₅₀	+36,5	+13,4
MOC ₇₅	+24	+19,9
6 minute walking trial	12	5

After 30 days of therapy for many indicators, the trend towards an increase in indicators continued: VC - by 19.6%, FEV1 - by 25.4%, PSV - by 22.7%, MOS25 - by 37.4%, MOS50 - by 36.5 %, MOS75 - by 14%, decrease in TRL - by 24.8% and the ratio of TOL / TRL - by 21%. Tolerance to physical activity for 30 days of the drug increased by 25.5%.

On the contrary, in the control group, we did not find significant changes in functional parameters, moreover, some indicators were reduced against the background of ongoing basic therapy. So, by the 10th day of therapy, the increase in FEV1 was 3%, MOS25 - 1.0%, MOS50 -13.4%, MOS75 - 19.9%, there was a decrease in VC - by 2.4%, PSV - by 17 %, an increase in the residual volume by 89%, and the ratio of OOL /

OEL - by 29.2%, which indicates an increase in the severity of emphysematous manifestations. The data of a 6-minute step test show a slight increase in the first 10 days of basic therapy, which amounted to 5%, and a month later, when the test was repeated, a decrease in exercise tolerance by 13% was noted.

Along with the improvement in functional parameters, there was a significant decrease in the severity of clinical symptoms of COPD in patients taking inhaled glycerosin. So in patients by the 10th day of treatment, it was possible to achieve a decrease in cough by 1.5 times, the amount of sputum secreted decreased by 1.3 times, and the severity of shortness of breath decreased by 1.8 times. By the end of 1 month of taking the drug, these symptoms decreased by 2.1; 2.2 and 2.2 times, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Clinical results of complex treatment with IG in patients with COPD

Clinical symptoms points	Research stages		
	Before treatment	After 10 days	After 1 month
Dyspnea	2,2±0,2	1,2±0,2	1,0±0,2*
Cough	2,6±0,1	1,8±0,1	1,2±0,1*
Sputum production	2,4±0,1	1,8±0,1	1,1±0,1*

Note: * - significance of differences between groups at the beginning of therapy and after 1 month. – $p < 0.001$.

The results of our work are consonant with the results of other similar studies (2,7) that have established a significant increase in functional pulmonary parameters in patients with COPD on the background of IG therapy, accompanied by an improvement in the clinical picture and quality of life of patients.

Thus, in the course of the conducted studies, a positive dynamics of ventilation indicators was established, all the main indicators of the function of external respiration improved, and tolerance to physical activity increased. Comprehensive treatment of COPD patients with the use of IG leads to a significant reduction in a number of major clinical manifestations of the disease already during the first 10 days of treatment and continues throughout the course of therapy.

The conducted studies allow us to conclude that glycerosin inhalation, providing high clinical and functional efficacy in the treatment of patients with COPD, is a well-effective drug in the basic therapy of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

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